

**MYSTICAL VIEWS, PRINCIPLES AND METHODS OF AVICENNA
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Abstract: The pedagogical principles and methods of the great scientist and philosopher Avicenna have been discussed in the article. Considerations include an individualized approach to the relationship between morality and education, and the practical application of knowledge. The teaching methods developed by Avicenna are also presented, including the system of questions and answers, the use of analogies and metaphors, the use of practical tasks, and the development of emotional intelligence. The influence of Avicenna's pedagogical ideas on modern education, including interactive teaching methods, taking into account the individual characteristics of students, and the development of emotional intelligence. The influence of Avicenna's pedagogical ideas on modern education, including interactive teaching methods, taking into account the individual characteristics of students, the development of ethical competence and the practical application of knowledge in real life.

Key words: pedagogy, intellect, thinking, individual, interactive methods, method, moral.

Intodaction

Avicenna, also known as Avicenna, was a prominent Persian scientist who lived in the IX th and XI th centuries. He became famous for his achievements in medicine, philosophy, and pedagogy. His work is an important contribution to these fields of knowledge and continues to influence modern education. Avicenna's early life, his studies and early scientific research laid the foundation for his future works and achievements. Philosophy and pedagogy were important areas of interest for Avicenna. He developed his own philosophical system based on a combination of Aristotelian and Neoplatonic philosophy. This system included the doctrines of nature, man, and the divine. In the field of pedagogy, Avicenna identified several basic principles, including an individual approach to learning, the development of critical thinking, the connection between education and morality, and the practical application of knowledge. His ideas and methods still influence modern teaching practices. [1]

Study Objectives

Avicenna developed several basic pedagogical principles that were important to his approach to teaching. They included an individual approach to each student, the development of critical thinking, the connection between education and morality, as well as the practical application of knowledge. These principles were fundamental to his educational philosophy and helped him create a unique educational system that is still relevant today. Avicenna attached particular importance to an individual approach for each student. He understood that every person has unique abilities and needs, and that is why education must be tailored to each student. He tried to create an environment in which students could express their potential and develop their abilities to the fullest. Avicenna considered the background and interests of each student to ensure effective learning. [2]

The idea that morality and education have some connection has been identified as one of the major tenets of Avicenna's educational philosophy. In his view, education should instill in students' strong moral principles and ethical ideals in addition to imparting knowledge. Avicenna observed his students' moral and ethical development and assisted them in realizing the value of virtues, moral behavior, and justice. Only then, in his opinion, would education be comprehensive and beneficial to society.

Results and discussion.

Avicenna attached particular importance to the practical application of knowledge. He believed that education should not only be theoretical, but also aimed at the practical application of acquired knowledge. The thinker actively involved students in practical tasks that helped them apply the acquired knowledge in real life. Practical training allowed students to better assimilate the material and understand its applicability, which contributed to their development and successful adaptation in society.

The teaching methods developed by the thinker were based on his philosophy of education. It offered a question-and-answer system that helped students actively participate in the learning process. This technique promoted the development of critical thinking and made it possible to test understanding of the material. Avicenna also used analogies and metaphors to explain complex concepts, which helped students understand the information better. The use of practical assignments was another teaching method that allowed students to apply their knowledge in practice and strengthen the connection between theory and real life. Finally, Avicenna placed great importance on the

development of emotional intelligence, which helped students develop emotional and social competence. [3]

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According to the scientific world, the development of ethical competence is an important aspect of modern education, inspired by the ideas of Avicenna. Students learn not only subject knowledge, but also principles of morality and ethics. This includes developing interpersonal skills, treating others with respect, and cultivating a culture of tolerance. Developing ethical competence helps students become responsible citizens and develop good values in their lives. [4]

Conclusion

At the conclusion of the article, it is clear that Avicenna's pedagogical principles and methods have a significant influence on modern education. An individual approach to learning, the development of critical thinking, the connection between education and morality, as well as the practical application of knowledge—all these principles perfectly correspond to the modern needs of the educational system. The methods developed by Avicenna, such as the question-and-answer system, the use of analogies and metaphors, the use of practical tasks, and the development of emotional intelligence, are also relevant and effective in modern teaching. Interactive teaching methods, taking into account the individual characteristics of students, developing ethical competence, and practical application of knowledge in real life—all of this received inspiration from the pedagogical ideas of Avicenna. Thus, Avicenna's contribution to education remains significant and relevant today.

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